

Impact of Impression Management and Self-Concept on Achievement Motivation and Academic Performance of Students

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ABSTRACT:

This study examines the relationship between the level of impression management and self-concept with achievement motivation and academic performance among students aged 16-30 years. The study adopted an estimated population sample of 200 individuals in carrying out the study, quantitative data were collected and analyzed by the use of correlation and regression analysis. The results reflected positive correlations with a high level of significance between impression management, self-concept, achievement motivation overt and academic performance. The analysis showed that impression management as well as self-concept correlated with achievement motivation and academic performance; though, the correlation of self-concept was stronger. The findings underscore the need for increasing students' self-concept and ability to manage first and second impressions as a way of increasing motivation and achievement. This paper provides important knowledge to educators and policymakers wishing to improve student outcomes and engagement.

Keywords: in nature: Impression Management, Self-Concept, Achievement Motivation, Academic Performance.

1. Introduction

Thus, recognizing the psychological and social antecedents in academic achievement context has a paramount important place in the current educational environment. Of all the antecedents to academic achievement, the roles of impression management and self-concept have stimulated much enquiry in educational psychology. These factors affect students' self-organizational identities, self-image on-top of affecting students' motivation to achieve and academic performance as identified by peer and educators.

1.1 Background of the Study:

From Leary and Kowalski (1990), impression management can be described as intentional actions taken by people with a view of controlling other's impressions about them; especially in organizations and among colleagues. Ad specifically noted that in academic settings, students use impression management techniques to gain favorable reaction from fellow students and professors explaining the impact on student motivation and course performance as explained by Rosenfeld et al. (1995). These strategies are most useful where social reward and recognition are highly indexed with academic performance in competitive society.

Likewise, self-concept; a personal view of abilities, identity and value; is a critical determinant of academic achievement. Positive self concept is defined as realistic, temporal and context specific appraisal of the self, they found that positive self concept is related to increased resilience and motivation, as well as enhanced achievement (Marsh and Martin, 2011). On the other hand, negative self concept may enhance feelings of inferiority and negative attitude towards achievement at school (Shavelson et al., 1976).

Academic motivation or the drive to achieve academic goals; intrinsic and extrinsic goals is the mediator between impression management, self-concept, and academic performance. Herman and colleagues state that purposefully high achieving student exhibit purpose, persistence and personal improvement orientation (Elliot and McGregor, 2001). Although prior research has explored each of these factors separately, the way in which they interact in academic environments and especially in culturally diverse countries as Pakistan has not yet been investigated.

1.2 Problem Statement:

As previously stated, academic performance is a common focus of research literatures, but few scholars investigate the moderation of IMP and self concept on achievement motivation and academic results simultaneously. In the context of Pakistan, where societal expectations and cultural norms significantly shape student behavior, understanding these factors is essential. This study addresses this gap by investigating the relationship between impression management, self-concept, achievement motivation, and academic performance among college and university students in Pakistan.

1.3 Objectives

- 1) Examine the relationship between impression management and academic performance.
- 2) Investigate the role of self-concept in influencing achievement motivation.
- 3) Analyze the combined impact of impression management and self-concept on academic performance.
- 4) Compare these factors among college and university students.

1.4 Research Questions

- 1) How does impression management influence students academic performance?
- 2) What role does self-concept play in shaping achievement motivation?
- 3) How do impression management and self-concept collectively impact academic performance?
- 4) Are there significant differences between college and university students regarding these factors?

1.5 Hypotheses

- 1) Impression management positively correlates with academic performance.
- 2) Self-concept positively correlates with achievement motivation.
- 3) Impression management and self-concept jointly predict academic performance.
- 4) University students demonstrate higher levels of achievement motivation compared to college students.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Impression Management:

According to Erving Goffman in his book published in 1959, impression management is defined as the roles that each of us plays in the everyday effort to control the information that others have regarding ourselves. Employees working in organizations apply impression management to make their instructors and peers think that they are competent (Leary & Kowalski, 1990). These may contain activities that involve; proactivity in classes, for example, taking the front row in a classroom, or acting “smart” by putting much emphasis on their achievements.

Some findings shows that IM is a strong precursor to academic achievement. For example, Rosenfeld et al. (1995) have substantiated that learners who use IM tactics tend to be closer to their teachers, which results in the improved quality of a grade. However, when people rely heavily on impression management and enactment stress, and fakeness while decreases the learning effect (Bolino et al., 2008).

2.2 Self-Concept:

Academic self concept refer to the perceptions that learners have about their academic ability (Shavelson et al 1976). This evaluation criterion has direct effects on the students motivational state, approaches to learn and achievement (Marsh & Martin, 2011).

The learners who have a positive academic self-concept have a tendency to set high achievement goals, work harder on a difficult content, and demonstrate hardness (Harter, 1999). Valentine et al. (2004) conducted a meta-synthesis and observed strong positive result of self-concept as to performance, which points to the need for strategies to promote positive self-concept and its value in promoting the student performance. On the same note, low self-concept leads to low performance resulting from self-doubt among the student (Bong & Skaalvik, 2003).

Self concept development is answered by the social comparison theory, feedback from teachers and family expectations and demands according to Marsh et al (2005). Hence, in collectivist culture such as the one adopted in Pakistan, family and community standards are very influential on students ‘self-identities (Rehman, & Azam, 2012).

2.3 Achievement Motivation:

Achievement motivation refers to an individual's desire to accomplish goals, succeed, and excel in tasks (McClelland, 1961). It is a critical determinant of academic success, as it drives students to engage in goal-directed behavior.

The 2 × 2 achievement goal framework developed by Elliot and McGregor (2001) categorizes achievement motivation into mastery-approach, mastery-avoidance, performance-approach, and performance-avoidance goals. Students with mastery-approach goals are driven by a desire to improve their competencies, while those with performance-approach goals aim to outperform others.

Research consistently shows that achievement motivation positively correlates with academic performance (Pintrich & De Groot, 1990). Students with high levels of achievement motivation tend to exhibit greater self-regulation, perseverance, and engagement in academic tasks (Wigfield & Eccles, 2002). However, extrinsic motivation, driven by external rewards or pressures, may lead to surface-level learning rather than deep understanding (Deci & Ryan, 1985).

2.4 The Interplay Between Impression Management, Self-Concept, and Achievement Motivation:

The interaction between impression management, self-concept, and achievement motivation has been examined in various studies. Leary and Kowalski (1990) affirms that effective impression management has the potential to improve an individual's self image as a result of social acceptance. Consequently, personal positive self-concept enhances intrinsic motivation in order to achieve considerable academic results.

Likewise, Schlenker (1980) suggested that impression management usually reflects achievement motive, as students employ them to acquire approval and increase their efficacy. However, when students over-depend on external reinforcement of their performance, there is a tendency of no manifestation of the internal drive towards performance and course work, not forgetting that this can have a negative impact on the long run performance of the learners as noted by Rosenfeld et al, 1995.

2.5 Academic Performance:

School achievement as an educational effectiveness index is a complex construct that depends on students' thinking, affective, and interpersonal processes. Studies have also shown Impression management, self concept and achievement motivation as predictors of academic achievement (Marsh et al., 2005).

Robbins et al., (2004) in his meta-analysis proved that academic self-concept and intrinsic motivation are the second and fourth robust predictors of college GPA respectively. Likewise, Bolino et al. (2008) identified that when such students practice adequate impression management technique, they can develop good relationship with their lecturers which in one way or another enhance their performance.

2.6 Cultural Considerations in Pakistan:

For collectivist cultures such as in Pakistan, cultural norms and family pressures severely shape students academic conduct (Rehman & Azam, 2012). The pursuit of family expectations makes the students to exhibit impression management techniques regardless the costs incurred on their intrinsic motivation.

Furthermore, educational practice in society determines student's self-esteem based on how well they perform in their classes (Saeed & Zyngier, 2012). This cultural requirement calls for a better appreciation of the relationship between impression management, self- concept and achievement motivation and academic achievement in Pakistan.

3. Methods

The present study used a quantitative research method to analyse the moderating role of impression management and self-concept on achievement motivation and academic performance of students. A survey method was used because it fitted the purpose of obtaining quantitative data from a heterogeneous population. A structured questionnaire was designed and constructed to assess impression management, self concept, achievement motivation and academic performance using standardized scales. In the current research, 200 participants aged were 16-30 years selected and collected through convenience sampling from college and universities in urban areas of Pakistan. For the purpose of gender diversity, the sample had an equal number of male and female students. Some statistical procedures like correlation and regression were applied to analyse the variables. The use of the quantitative approach helped in the pulling off of an objective measure and explanation of the research findings while the survey method helped in the achievement of fast and efficient ways of getting data out of the research sample of college and university students.

4. Results and Discussion

The result shall be discussed in this chapter because this chapter presents the results of the research as found in the study. The purpose of this research was to find correlation of the impression management and self-concept with achievement motivation and academic performances of students of 16-30 years old. Structured questionnaires administered to 200 participants were statistical analyzed.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics:

The original data regarding demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in the Table 4.1. The subjects selected were 100 males (50 %) and 100 females (50 %) with their age varying between 16 and 30 years with mean age of 22.5 years.

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Variable	Categories	Frequency (N=20)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	100	50%
	Female	100	50%
Age	16-20	70	35%
	21-25	95	47.5%
	26-30	35	17.5%

4.2 Correlation Analysis:

Pearsons correlation was used to determine significance of the studied relationships between variables impression management, self-concepts, achievement motivation and academic performance. The findings as shown in Table 4.3 are as follows.

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix

Variable	Impression Management	Self-concept	Achievement Motivation	Academic Performance
Impression Management	1.00	0.45**	0.38**	0.32**
Self-concept	0.45**	1.00	0.51**	0.48**
Achievement Motivation	0.38**	0.51**	1.00	0.56**
Academic Performance	0.32**	0.48**	0.56**	1.00

(**p < 0.01)

The correlation coefficients further showed that all the variables are positively related, though significantly. It was found that self presentation and self image share a moderately positive correlation, both of these and achievement motivation as well as academic performance were positively significant.

4.3 Regression Analysis:

The predictive effects of impression management and self-concept on achievement motivation and academic performance were analysed through regression analysis. The results are presented in table form within the following table: Table 4.3

Table 4.3: Regression Analysis Results

Dependent Variable	Predictor Variables	β	t	p-value	R ²
Achievement Motivation	Impression Management	0.34	4.32	< 0.001	0.42
	Self-concept	0.47	6.10	< 0.001	
Academic Performance	Impression Management	0.29	3.85	< 0.001	0.39
	Self-concept	0.41	5.72	< 0.001	

The results of the regression analysis demonstrated that both impression management and self-concept were found to be significant with the achievement motivation and academic performance with the p-value 0.000. Self-concept produced a higher value of β meaning it played a larger role in the prediction of achievement motivation and academic performance than impression management.

4.4 Discussion

In support of the analysis, the findings show that while impression management and self-concept significantly predicted achievement motivation and academic performance among the students. The moderate relationship between impression management and self concept mean that these element

interactively influence the learning behavior. Self-presentation was established as a moderator implying that the extent to which students present an organised, positive impression correlates with achievement motivation and better grades.

Self-concept was more robust predictor of both achievement motivation and academic performance, for which focus should be achieved through students' perceptions of themselves in academic contexts. Such conclusions imply that raising students self-organised concept and impression regulation might be crucial for increasing their motivation and achievement.

Thus, this work is useful in providing information relating to the determinants of academic performance. It is reassuring that the study is quantitative in nature and has a massive sample size; such observations may help in designing educational interventions to enhance various learners' academic achievement in different settings.

5. Conclusion

The present study supports influence of impression management and self-concept on achievement motivation as well as academic performance among students of 16 to 30 years of age. The results suggest the trend that impression management and self concept have positive relationship with achievement motivation and academic performance, where self concept was seen to be a better predictor than the impression management. Concisely, these findings imply that efforts for developing positive self-concept and improving the ability to manage impressions may be significant for increasing students motivation and achievement. Through the insights gained in the study, educators and policymakers can ideally implement programs that will form the basis for enhancing students psychological as well as their academic achievements.

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